

TRANSNATURE

Policy Recommendations: EGTC ZASNET and Meseta Ibérica

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Policy Recommendation 01

Improving the Effectiveness of Cross-Border Governance Through the Integration of Public Authorities with Legal Environmental Competences

Main problem: Despite ZASNET EGTC being the designated managing entity of the Meseta Ibérica Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, entities holding statutory competences in environmental protection and biodiversity conservation in both Spain and Portugal are not members of the EGTC, leading to a governance structure that lacks the direct involvement of the legally competent authorities.

Addressees: ZASNET; Junta de Castilla y León; Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas (ICNF)

Recommendation: The effective governance of the Meseta Ibérica Transboundary Biosphere Reserve (TBR) requires that its designated managing entity possess the institutional capacity to ensure integrated, participatory, and sustainable management of the Reserve, in full alignment with the Statutory Framework of the World Network of Biosphere Reserves (UNESCO General Conference Resolution 28 C/2.4, 1995). This Framework explicitly requires the establishment of a competent authority or institutional mechanism entrusted with the implementation of the policies and management plans specific to each Biosphere Reserve.

Currently, the ZASNET European Grouping of Territorial Cooperation (EGTC) acts as the sole entity responsible for the unified governance of the TBR, pursuant to the legal framework set out in Regulation (EC) No. 1082/2006, as amended by Regulation (EU) No. 1302/2013, designed to facilitate cross-border, transnational and interregional cooperation within the European Union. However, its current membership is limited to municipalities, associations of local entities, and provincial authorities. A key structural limitation therefore persists: neither the Junta de Castilla y León (Spain) nor the Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas (ICNF, Portugal) - the two public authorities vested with statutory and executive competences in environmental policy and biodiversity conservation within the territory of the TBR - currently hold membership in the EGTC. Their exclusion significantly constrains the governance system's operational capacity and undermines the principles of subsidiarity and administrative efficiency that underpin the EGTC regulatory framework.

It is therefore recommended that:

1. The competent environmental authorities of both Member States, namely the Junta de Castilla y León and the ICNF, be formally integrated as full members of ZASNET EGTC, in accordance with Article 3(1) of Regulation (EC) No. 1082/2006, which expressly allows for the membership of regional and national public authorities.
2. Such integration should be pursued to ensure that the TBR's cross-border governance arrangements are fully aligned with the national and regional environmental competences legally assigned to these authorities under domestic law, thereby enhancing the EGTC's institutional legitimacy and operational effectiveness.

Strengthening the institutional composition of ZASNET EGTC through the inclusion of these competent authorities will consolidate its legal and administrative capacity to implement the management objectives

of the TBR, while ensuring respect for the limitations set by EU law concerning non-transferable public (particularly police and regulatory Powers, according to Recital 13 of Regulation (EC) No. 1082/2006).

Added value: Integrating the Junta de Castilla y León and the Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas (ICNF) as full members of the ZASNET EGTC would enable enhanced horizontal and vertical coordination within the governance framework of the Meseta Ibérica Transboundary Biosphere Reserve. Horizontal coordination would be strengthened through structured cooperation between Spanish and Portuguese environmental administrations, fostering harmonised approaches to conservation planning and joint management actions. Vertical coordination would be improved by ensuring that local and provincial initiatives are fully integrated into regional and national biodiversity frameworks, thereby enhancing policy coherence and the effectiveness of conservation strategies.

Furthermore, the integration of the competent environmental authorities into the ZASNET EGTC should also entail an improvement in the financial capacity of the entity, insofar as their participation would reasonably be expected to bring additional institutional funding and resources to support the governance of the Meseta Ibérica TBR. For further considerations regarding the enhancement of funding mechanisms and financial capacity, see Policy Recommendation 06.

Policy Recommendation 02

Legal and Statutory Alignment of ZASNET EGTC for Effective Governance of the Meseta Ibérica TBR

Main problem: The founding convention of ZASNET EGTC and its 2010 statutes, while containing general provisions on cross-border environmental cooperation, were adopted prior to the 2015 designation of the Meseta Ibérica Transboundary Biosphere Reserve (TBR) and have not been normatively adapted to reflect this new legal and functional context. In particular, they do not confer any specific mandate or defined management competences regarding the governance of the TBR. Moreover, subsequent amendments to ZASNET's organisational structure have neither obtained the legally required approval from the competent Portuguese ministry nor been duly published in the Portuguese Official Gazette (*Diário da República*), thereby generating legal uncertainty as to their validity and raising concerns regarding full compliance with binding Portuguese legal requirements.

Addressees: ZASNET EGTC

Recommendation: In order to ensure the lawful and effective governance of the Meseta Ibérica Transboundary Biosphere Reserve (TBR), it is recommended that the ZASNET European Grouping of Territorial Cooperation (EGTC) undertake a formal legal alignment of its founding documents and organisational structure with the requirements laid down in Regulation (EC) No. 1082/2006, as amended by Regulation (EU) No. 1302/2013, and the Portuguese implementing provisions established under Decree-Law No. 376/2007 of 8 November. In particular, ZASNET should:

1. Ensure compliance with national authorisation and publication requirements: Pursuant to Article 5 of Decree-Law No. 376/2007, any amendments to the ZASNET convention or statutes - including changes to its membership composition (such as the 2016 withdrawal of the Douro Superior Municipal Association and the subsequent accession of Bragança Municipality) and any organisational adjustments designed to establish a dedicated management unit for the TBR - must be subject to prior authorisation by the competent Portuguese Minister responsible for regional development. Although these changes were approved internally by ZASNET's General Assembly, there is no evidence of approval following the procedure laid down in Article 5(10) of Decree-Law No. 376/2007, nor of their publication in the *Diário da República* as required by Article 7. The absence of ministerial approval and publication casts doubt on the validity and enforceability of ZASNET's current governance arrangements.
2. Explicit statutory recognition of TBR management functions: The statutes of ZASNET, adopted in 2010 prior to the UNESCO designation of the Meseta Ibérica TBR (2015), currently provide only general references to cross-border cooperation in the fields of environment, tourism, culture, enterprise development, depopulation mitigation, and project implementation. It is therefore necessary to revise the statutes to expressly include the objectives, competences, and functions of ZASNET as the entity entrusted with the unified governance of the TBR, thereby providing a clear legal basis for the fulfilment of its management mandate.

Ensuring legal regularity through the proper authorisation and publication of all amendments, and adapting the statutes to reflect the specific management objectives of the TBR, constitute essential measures to guarantee the legal effectiveness of ZASNET's organisational structure and to ensure compliance with the commitments undertaken by the EGTC within the framework of UNESCO's MaB Programme.

Added value: Strengthens transparency by ensuring public disclosure of ZASNET's organisational acts and institutional information.

Policy Recommendation 03

Promoting Community-Based Energy Projects in the Meseta Ibérica

Main problem: The emergence of large-scale renewable energy projects promoted by actors disconnected from local communities in the territory of the Meseta Ibérica and often failing to deliver tangible socioeconomic benefits for local populations has raised significant concerns among stakeholders. These initiatives typically follow a top-down approach, offering only limited opportunities for meaningful community participation. This dynamic poses risks to the conservation of biodiversity and the landscape and may lead to adverse socio-economic impacts. Furthermore, it undermines public acceptance of the energy transition and exacerbates existing asymmetries between the interests of project developers and local management over natural resources.

Addressees: ZASNET EGTC, local authorities, chambers of commerce, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), citizens, associations, civic platforms and cooperatives.

Recommendation: To ensure that the energy transition within the Meseta Ibérica contributes effectively to territorial equity as well as environmental and energy justice - going beyond appropriate spatial planning, respectful of protected areas and sites, and the integration of renewable energy in sectoral and territorial planning instruments, as already highlighted by the Scientific Council of the Spanish MaB Committee (2023) - it is recommended that public authorities and ZASNET EGTC actively support the development of community-based energy projects anchored in models of local ownership, participatory governance, and equitable benefit-sharing.

Such an approach would give effect to the Lima Action Plan (UNESCO, 2017), which establishes that Biosphere Reserves shall adopt a participatory approach involving local communities with the aim of conserving biodiversity, restoring and enhancing ecosystem services, and promoting the sustainable use of natural resources. Moreover, fostering community energy models is fully aligned with the Strategic Guidelines on Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency in the Spanish Network of Biosphere Reserves, as set out in the 2014-2023 Action Plan, which call for “promoting new forms of governance for sustainable energy” and for “integrating renewable energy solutions with the core functions of Biosphere Reserves”.

The current EU regulatory framework - particularly Directive (EU) 2018/2001 (RED II) and Directive (EU) 2019/944 - explicitly recognises the role of renewable energy communities and citizen energy communities, requiring Member States to provide enabling conditions for their creation and operation. This obligation has been transposed into national law in both Portugal, through Decree-Law No. 15/2022, and Spain, through Law 24/2013, establishing the legal basis for decentralised, participatory energy systems that prioritise local value. In this context, it is recommended to:

1. Facilitate the establishment of community energy initiatives within the Reserve by ensuring comprehensive administrative, financial, and capacity-building support for citizens, small and medium-sized enterprises, civic platforms, associations, and cooperatives.
2. Promote the direct participation of local authorities in energy communities and foster their establishment and operation through patrimonial support measures, including the allocation or temporary transfer of public assets, land, or infrastructure under favourable conditions, to facilitate their development and ensure their long-term sustainability.

3. Promote the development of transboundary energy communities, leveraging the EU's legal framework for cross-border cooperation in energy generation, sharing, supply, and other energy services.
4. Encourage the reinvestment of energy revenues into local services, biodiversity protection, and rural development, in alignment with the objectives of the Biosphere Reserve. In accordance with RED II and Directive 2019/944 - which require that the primary purpose of energy communities be to provide environmental, economic, or social community benefits rather than financial profits- community energy initiatives should be encouraged to design revenue-sharing mechanisms that prioritise reinvestment in the territory and strengthen long-term ecological and social resilience.
5. Actively promote the use of existing financial instruments and support programmes available in both Spain and Portugal (subject to the availability and opening of the corresponding public calls) to support the development of community energy projects. These include, in Spain, national programmes such as *CE-Implementa* (IDAE), the support schemes for self-consumption and energy communities under the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan, as well as regional programmes implemented by Castilla y León. In Portugal, they comprise the support schemes of the *Fundo Ambiental*, particularly the calls for the creation of *Comunidades de Energia Renovável* and *Autoconsumo Coletivo*, co-financed through the PRR (*Plano de Recuperação e Resiliência*). These public instruments may be complemented by innovative financing mechanisms such as green bonds, cooperative investment schemes, and partnerships with ethical or impact investors.
6. Ensure the establishment of synergies and structured cooperation with the Duero-Douro EGTC, whose territorial scope almost entirely coincides with that of the Meseta Ibérica Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, making use of its recognised expertise and proven track record in implementing and managing community-based energy projects, with a view to facilitating the effective fulfilment of the above recommendations.

Added value: Community-based energy projects may contribute directly to reversing rural depopulation trends by anchoring economic activity, creating skilled jobs, and fostering local empowerment. By allowing communities to co-own and manage energy resources, these initiatives enhance resilience, strengthen territorial identity, and offer sustainable alternatives to extractive development models that provide little or no return to the territory.

Policy Recommendation 04

Strengthening Participatory Mechanisms and Democratic Representation within ZASNET

Main problem: Adequate stakeholder integration is crucial against the backdrop of the Man and the Biosphere (MaB) programme. However, different regulatory frameworks, weak institutional arrangements, diverse stakeholders, and linguistic and cultural barriers make it difficult to establish adequate participation mechanisms. Improving participation mechanisms has been identified as one of ZASNET's main challenges.

Addressees: ZASNET EGTC, local, regional and national authorities.

Recommendation: MaB Programme is a particular solution regarding biodiversity protection where human communities are consistently integrated in a defined geographical space of particular value. When biosphere reserves include the human element as a value of the protected area, participation becomes a crucial issue. More intensively than other instruments of protection, reserves within the MaB Programme require integrating the local public and all relevant stakeholders into the management of the area.

In fact, according to Hangzhou Strategic Action Plan for the UNESCO's Man and Biosphere (MAB) Programme and its World Network of Biosphere Reserves (2026-2035), reserves of the biosphere should be model territories for the meaningful participation of stakeholders and rights holders, recognising the importance of Local Communities in biodiversity conservation. According to this, Action Target 15 foresees that, by 2035, all concerned biosphere reserves should ensure the full and effective participation of Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities in their designation, management and governance processes.

Against this backdrop, the complexity of the human interests at stake must be considered alongside the implications arising from the transboundary character of the reserve. To address these challenges and to ensure adequate and effective participation of local communities and other stakeholders in its governance, a range of complementary actions may be pursued, including the following:

1. Identifying different categories of actors and stakeholders in order to design tailored forms of participation, thereby enhancing the capacity for all relevant interests to be duly taken into account.
2. Introducing consultation mechanisms and forms of institutional participation beyond the existing governing bodies, with a view to integrating all potential stakeholders into decision-making processes and strategic planning.
3. Conducting structured consultation processes among stakeholders to identify legal, institutional, and practical barriers that hinder effective participation.
4. Ensuring sensitivity to gender-related issues, in accordance with the Hangzhou Strategic Action Plan (Action 21).

Added value: Any meaningful consolidation of a reserve of the biosphere implies the involvement of local communities, beyond their representative institutions. This can only be achieved through effective participation tools allowing all potential stakeholders, possibly holding different, even competing interests, in decisions regarding the reserve and, particularly, in designing its strategic goals.

Policy Recommendation 05

Enhancing Rooting and Recognition of ZASNET in the territory

Main problem: The main goal of a MaB area is to preserve a historically meaningful set of relations between human communities, landscapes and ecosystems. This objective is closely linked to a shared local identity, through which the reserve is perceived by the local population as a space for the development of a distinctive way of life. To the extent that local communities do not perceive the project as their own - by actively converging in the definition of its identity, strategies and modes of management - the biosphere reserve cannot fully achieve its objectives as a protected area.

Addressees: ZASNET EGTC, local authorities.

Recommendation: It appears to be a shared perception that ZASNET has so far functioned as an empty label, primarily aimed at promoting local cultural and natural assets as a tourist destination. To some extent, the ZASNET project is perceived as being oriented towards external audiences rather than local communities. There remains significant room for improvement in terms of recognition and appropriation of the reserve by the local population.

This recommendation is closely linked to the one concerning participatory mechanisms and democratic representation (PR04), since no meaningful territorial rooting can occur without the active involvement of local communities. Nevertheless, beyond the measures previously suggested, additional targeted strategies could be pursued to strengthen local attachment to the project. Such strategies necessarily depend on the specific characteristics of local stakeholders and therefore require a careful identification of different categories of local actors.

On this basis, the management of the reserve should design tailored communication strategies aimed at fostering local identification with the project. At the same time, there is a risk of instrumentalising local public opinion if information is reduced to mere promotion or advertising. For this reason, any meaningful strategy of territorial rooting should strike a balanced combination of information, communication and participation, with a view to building a shared identity that lies at the core of the reserve's overall strategy.

Added value: Identification of the local population with the reserve is an essential condition for any MaB area to function properly. For this reason, strategies aimed at enhancing the recognition of ZASNET among local actors are necessary. Without this, the reserve is at risk of losing credibility as a viable and convincing project.

Policy Recommendation 06

Enhancing the Funding Mechanisms and Financial Capacity of ZASNET

Main problem: The lack of resources can prevent adopting ambitious and innovative policies, which are essential to provide substance to a complex project such as a biosphere reserve, which demand multifaceted strategies aligned with an adequate integration of human communities in the protected area.

Addressees: ZASNET EGTC, local, regional and national authorities.

Recommendation: A lack of funding is an endemic challenge for most public-interest projects. This difficulty is compounded by the institutional and substantive complexity involved. To secure adequate and sustainable financial support, it is essential to rely on the cooperation of institutional actors. Accordingly, public stakeholders, particularly the Spanish *Diputaciones Provinciales* and the Portuguese *Associações de Municípios*, should be substantially involved in designing financial arrangements aligned with a clearly defined and agreed-upon strategy for the biosphere reserve. Additionally, funding from regional and national authorities, as well as private partners, should be raised. In any case, it seems clear that, in connection with PR 04 and 05, rooting the project in the territory, as well as developing sound strategies for participation by local stakeholders, would help persuade regional and national authorities to allocate resources to ZASNET. This also relates to PR 01, insofar as the involvement of authorities with environmental protection competences should create incentives for them to commit the resources necessary to ensure the effective and sustainable management of the biosphere reserve.

Action Target 23 of the Hangzhou Strategic Action Plan for UNESCO's Man and the Biosphere (MaB) Programme and its World Network of Biosphere Reserves (2026-2035) provides that adequate institutional support in terms of financial and human resources must be ensured for biosphere reserves. Accordingly, by 2028, biosphere reserves, with the support of their respective governments, must have sufficient budgetary allocations and staffing to fulfil their functions, as well as the necessary resources and capacity to implement the Plan. This objective requires a firm funding commitment from the authorities associated with ZASNET, driven by local action and aligned with the international strategic goals of the MaB Programme.

To overcome chronic underfunding, a multi-source financing platform could be developed that combines public contributions with private sponsorship, philanthropic grants, and innovative instruments such as crowdfunding, environmental impact bonds, or partnerships with local foundations for community-based projects. Engaging regional and national authorities, as well as private partners, in the co-design of financial strategies, in line with PR01, could prove decisive. Such an approach must be accompanied by transparent and accountable governance arrangements, in accordance with PR04.

Added value: Improving and enhancing sources of funding allows for the development of effective policies strengthening the goals of the MaB project in the area, contributing to preserving the biosphere, preventing depopulation and maintaining the cultural and natural values of the area